

Problems of the rehabilitation system development in Ukraine during the War

The development of the rehabilitation system (RS) in Ukraine has been put on the back burner for decades. Now that the country has been in a full-scale war for more than a year, the development of the RS has become a promising and crucial area of work for the relevant ministries. It is worth noting that persons liable for military service aged 18 to 60 are subject to general mobilisation, and these individuals make up the bulk of the working-age population. Accordingly, if this age group does not receive quality rehabilitation services and cannot return to pre-martial law life and work after the end of martial law, it will be of great economic importance and will cause damage to the country's economy.

The issue of rehabilitation development arose in 2014 with the start of the Anti-Terrorist Operation (ATO) in Eastern Ukraine. Accordingly, the number of patients in need of rehabilitation began to grow in 2014. About 9,000 servicemen have been injured since the beginning of the ATO in 2014. More than 121 thousand soldiers were granted the status of combatants [7]. Thus, according to the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, in 2015 and 2016, more than 10,400 participants of the ATO received psychological rehabilitation at the expense of the state budget [5]. Since February 2022, the need for rehabilitation services has increased dramatically, and medical facilities have not been physically prepared to provide a large number of services. Unfortunately, accurate data on the number of servicemen and women in need of rehabilitation services, including prosthetics, is currently classified by the Ministry of Defence of Ukraine. According to the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, between 24 February 2022 and 13 March 2023, 13,734 people among the civilian population alone were injured [12]. There are more than ten thousand people who have undergone certain amputations. They will need prosthetic and orthopaedic products [9]. Obviously, in order to provide assistance to such a large number of patients, there needs to be a sufficient number of rehabilitation centres and specialists. In 2016, less than 30 institutions provided rehabilitation services to ATO veterans in Ukraine [3, p. 6-12]. According to the National Health Service of Ukraine (NHSU), as of March 2023, they contracted 244 medical institutions with inpatient rehabilitation services for rehabilitation packages [11]. This is the largest number of medical institutions in the history of Ukraine that will provide rehabilitation services. The reason for such a large volume of contracting is the flagship project of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine "Development of the Rehabilitation Care System" and the funding of the relevant NHSU rehabilitation packages [8]. It remains to be seen how many patients these medical facilities will be

able to accommodate and whether their capacity will be sufficient. It is important that rehabilitation services in Ukraine should be provided to all patients free of charge.

It is worth noting the existing shortage of rehabilitation specialists. According to statistics, in December 2020, there were 68 doctors of physical and rehabilitation medicine (FRM doctors), 395 doctors of physical therapy and sports medicine, and 831 physiotherapists in the country [1, p. 59]. For comparison, in Canada, there are 25,000 physical therapists and 9,000 occupational therapists per 35 million people [10]. As of March 2023, 1691 rehabilitation medicine doctors and almost 7,000 rehabilitation specialists were registered in the Electronic Healthcare System in Ukraine [11]. The NHSU notes that the number of users in the Electronic Healthcare System will continue to grow, as the registration of all healthcare professionals continues until all 100% of healthcare facilities and, accordingly, 100% of healthcare professionals working in them are registered [6]. In any case, the increase in the number of specialists should be made up of graduates. It takes 8 years to train an FRM doctor, and 5 years to train a physical therapist or occupational therapist. If we take into account the number of applicants for these specialties, we can note an increase in the period from 2018 to 2020, but already in 2021 there is a sharp decline in the supply of specialty 227 "Physical therapy, occupational therapy" at the first (bachelor's) level of education by 39.5% and at the second (master's) level of education by 23.7% [1, p.63]. In the period 2018-2022, less than 100 graduates obtained the specialty 227 "Physical Therapy, Occupational Therapy" at the second (master's) level of education [1, p.63]. If the trend continues, the demand for specialists in this speciality will not be met, and medical institutions will not be able to cover the existing number of patients with their services.

Another option to increase the number of FRM doctors could be the secondary specialisation of doctors of other specialties. In this case, specialisation lasts four months [2]. The limitation of this option is that the application for specialisation can usually be submitted only once a year, a limited number of educational institutions provide specialisation, and the number of graduates does not exceed several dozen. This option of increasing the number of specialists could meet the needs, provided that specialisation courses are held 2-3 times a year. Another problem with this method is the need for a specialist to first work for three years in the major speciality before being legally entitled to a secondary specialisation.

The quality of training of specialists and the quality of rehabilitation services they provide require special attention. In 2016, members of the World Health Organization (WHO) advisory mission noted that "immediate organisation of education and training courses for rehabilitation professionals with international support is needed" [4, p. 23]. The report also stated that "rehabilitation professionals are not trained by international standards" [4, p. 22]. Thus, it can be understood that the quality of professionals and, accordingly, the services they provided were low and did not meet the required international standards. Patients were the first to suffer from such services. It is currently difficult to assess the quality of rehabilitation services, but given that the reform of this area is still ongoing, it is unlikely that much progress

has been made in RS since 2016. It is the quality of RS that could be the subject of further research.

It can be concluded that RS in Ukraine is developing rapidly, as well as the number of patients in need. A considerable step for the development of RS could be to increase the number of specialists, which would create competition in the service market and, as a result, encourage specialists to develop under the international standards. An equally important factor in the development of RS could be the state order for rehabilitation specialities, as well as relevant changes in the system of secondary specialisation of doctors.

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